

MedVetKlebs	WP1: <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> from human and animal faeces	Rev. 3 14 th May 2019
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Procedure to isolate *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from human or animal faeces

1. Enrich the sample by use of an enrichment broth (**Luria-Bertani broth with 10 mg/L of ampicillin final concentration**). Trypto-Casein Soy broth (TSB) can be used instead of LB. Take a swab or a loopful (10 µL) of faeces material, inoculate in 10 mL of broth, mix, and incubate the suspension at **37 °C ± 1°C for 24 h ± 1 h**.
2. Following 24h incubation, using a 10µl loop, streak for single colonies onto the surface of a small petri dish (90 mm) of SCAI medium and incubate at **37°C ± 1°C for 48 h ± 1 h**. Sometimes, typical colonies (see SCAI medium procedure) can be recognized already after 24h culture on plates.

Purification and Identification of suspect *K. pneumoniae* colonies

Typical *Klebsiella* spp. colonies are yellow on SCAI medium.

3. Select suspect *Klebsiella pneumoniae* colonies¹ (if there are several morphotypes, take one or two of each) from each plate for subculture and bacterial identification. **Sweep the remaining plate content and freeze it at -80°C (for mixed colonies sequencing)** using CryoBank tubes or equivalent (e.g. *in house* BHI + 15% glycerol medium).
4. Streak the selected colonies¹ onto the surface of a non-selective agar (e.g. LB or TSA) medium in a manner which will allow isolated colonies to develop. Incubate plates at 37 °C ± 1°C for 24 h ± 1 h.
5. Determine species ID in all purified suspect *K. pneumoniae* colonies using MALDI-TOF MS and/or qPCR ID phylogroups.
6. Freeze only isolates confirmed as *Klebsiella pneumoniae* complex at -80°C using CryoBank tubes or equivalent (e.g. BHI + 15% glycerol medium). Store only one isolate *per* morphotype.

¹NOTE: If colonies are numerous and close to each other, re-isolate the colony on another SCAI agar plate to control for purity. Incubate for up to 48h.